

Lab protocols to study Solute Carrier Transporters

Ligation Independent Cloning of transporter gene into BacMam vector

ID: SP000T-P

Authors	¹ David B. Sauer, ¹ Huanyu Li, ¹ Sagar Raturi, ¹ Andreea Scacioc, ¹ Tina Bohstedt, ¹ Abilasha Balakrishnan
Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford. Oxford, UK

Protocol description

This protocol is used to clone the gene of interest into a BacMam vector (pHTBV1.1 in this case) in a ligation-free manner, which can subsequently be used to transpose the gene of interest into a bacmid for transfecting insect cells.

Materials

Biological materials:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ One Shot™ Mach1™ T1 Phage-Resistant Chemically Competent E. Coli, (Thermo Scientific, catalog number: C862003)▪ pHTBV1.1 vectors (LIC adapted)¹▪ Primers: The primers should have the 5' and 3' extensions indicated in Table 1.
Reagents:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Herculanase II Fusion DNA Polymerase (Agilent technologies, catalog Number: 600675)▪ dNTPs▪ BsaI-HF®v2 (20 units/μl) (NEB, Catalog number R3733S)▪ BseRI (4 units/μl) (NEB, Catalog number R0581S)▪ BfuAI (5 units/μl) (NEB, Catalog number R0701S)▪ BveI* (ThermoFisher, Catalog number ER1741)▪ BveI* (ThermoFisher, # ER1741)▪ DpNI (NEB, catalog number R0176S)▪ QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, catalog number 28104)▪ Sucrose for molecular biology (Sigma Aldrich, catalog number S0389)▪ GeneJET Plasmid Miniprep Kit (ThermoFisher, catalog number: K0502)
Equipment:	

Reagents setup

Procedure

1. PCR reaction:

1.1 Prepare the following PCR reaction mixture:

5x HercII buffer	5 μL
10 mM dNTP mix	0.75 μL
HercII Polymerase	0.25 μL
5 μM Primers	1.5 μL
Template DNA (2.5 ng/μl)	2.5 ng/μL
Water (adjust to make up to 50 μL)	

3. T4 DNA Polymerase treatment of vector:

3.1 Prepare the following reaction mixture:

Digested plasmid	50 µL
10X Buffer 2.1 or CutSmart (NEB)	10 µL
25 mM dNTP*	10 µL
BSA (NEB)	1 µL
100 mM DTT	5 µL
T4 DNA Polymerase (NEB)	2.5 µL
Water(adjust to make up to 100 µL)	

*Check required dNTP in **Table 1**.

3.2 Incubate for 30 minutes at 22°C, then 20 minutes at 75°C .

4. Insert preparation (required if the template used for the PCR has the same antibiotic marker as the cloning vector):

4.1 DpnI treatment of PCR products:

4.1.1 Dilute DpnI enzyme 20 times in CutSmart buffer, add 1 µl to PCR product and incubate at 37°C for 1 hour.

4.1.2 Purify PCR products using QIAquick PCR Purification Kit.

4.2 T4 DNA Polymerase treatment of PCR products:

4.2.1 Prepare the following reaction mixture:

PCR product	5 µL
10x NEB2.1 buffer	1 µL
25 mM required dNTP*	1 µL
100 mM DTT	0.5 µL
BSA (NEB)	0.1 µL
NEB T4 DNA Polymerase	0.25 µL
Water(adjust to make up to 10 µL)	

*Check required dNTP in **Table 1**.

4.2.2 Incubate for 30 minutes at 22°C, then 20 minutes at 75°C in a thermocycler/water bath.

5. Annealing and transformation:

5.1 For annealing, mix 1 µL of T4 treated plasmid with 3 µL of T4 treated insert. Include one vector negative and one insert negative control (use 5 µL of insert if transformation fails).

5.2 Incubate for a minimum of 30 min (preferably up to 1-2 hours) at 22°C (approximately RT), then keep on ice.

5.3 Add the reaction mixture to 40 µL of competent *E. coli* MACH-1 cells.

5.4 Incubate on ice for 30 min, then heat-shock at 42°C for 45 seconds.

5.5 Chill briefly on ice, then add 900 µL* of SOC medium.

5.6 Incubate for at least 60 min at 37°C in a static incubator.

5.7 Plate 100 µL of transformation onto LB-agar containing 5% sucrose and appropriate antibiotic (see **Table 1**).

NOTE: Prepare 5% sucrose from a filter sterilised 25% (w/v) sucrose stock.

Antibiotic	Indicated concentration (µg/mL)
Carbenicillin	50
Kanamycin	50
Choramphenicol	34
Gentamycin	7
Streptomycin or Spectinomycin	50

5.8 Grow overnight (until colonies appear) by incubating at 37°C.

NOTE: *For difficult-to-clone targets, prepare a 96-deep-well block containing 500 µL of SOC medium, add transformation mix, then incubate in a shaker at 37°C, 700 rpm. Plate 100 µL onto LB-agar containing appropriate antibiotic (see **Table 1**).

6. PCR Screen:

6.1 Perform colony PCR on the colonies or perform a plasmid miniprep and sequence the insert DNA using the primers shown in **Table 1** and grow overnight cultures. Cryopreserve the positive clones at -80°C.

Table 1:

Vector Name	Tags for Purification	dNTP for Vector	dNTP for Insert	5' LIC Primer Extension	3' LIC Primer Extension	Screening Primers	bp added during PCR
pHTBV1.1-LIC	C-terminal His ₁₀ +Flag	dCTP	dGTP	TTAAGAAGGAGAGATA TACTATG	GATTGGAAGTAGA GGTTCCTGTC	pHTBV-F+R	~380
pHTBV1.1-NTSIII-H10-LIC	N-terminal Twin-Strep+His ₁₀	dGTP	dCTP	TACTTCCAATCCATG	TATCCACCTTTACT GTCA	pHTBV-F+R	~500
pHTBV1.1-NSIII-10H-GFPT	N-terminal Twin-Strep+His ₁₀ +GFP	dGTP	dCTP	TACTTCCAATCCATG	TATCCACCTTTACT GTCA	GFP- fwd+pHTBV-R	~350
pHTBV1.1-NTGST-10H-LIC	N-terminal GST+His ₁₀	dGTP	dCTP	TACTTCCAATCCATG	TATCCACCTTTACT GTCA	GST- fwd+pHTBV-R	~400
pHTBV1.1-CT10H-SIII-LIC	C-terminal His ₁₀ +Twin-Strep	dCTP	dGTP	TTAAGAAGGAGAGATA TACTATG	GATTGGAAGTAGA GGTTCCTGTC	pHTBV-F+R	~450
pHTBV1.1-CTGFP-SIII-10H	C-terminal GFP+Twin-Strep+His ₁₀	dCTP	dGTP	TTAAGAAGGAGAGATA TACTATG	GATTGGAAGTAGA GGTTCCTGTC	pHTBV-F+GFP- rev	~350
pHTBV1.1-SecNH-Bio	N-terminal His ₆ +C-terminal Avi (RTPmu signal)	dGTP	dCTP	TACTTCCAATCCATG	TATCCACCTTTACT GCT	pHTBV-F+R	~500

Additional notes

1: The type of DNA polymerase and restriction enzymes can vary depending on the experimental requirement or individual preferences.

2: Use molecular biology grade water for all PCR and cloning steps and ultrapure water to prepare other reagents.

Data availability

References

1: Fornwald, J.A., Lu, Q., Boyce, F.M., Ames, R.S. (2016). Gene Expression in Mammalian Cells Using BacMam, a Modified Baculovirus System. In: Murhammer, D. (eds) Baculovirus and Insect Cell Expression Protocols. Methods in Molecular Biology, vol 1350. Humana Press, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3043-2_5

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